

DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MINIATURIZED ELECTROSTATIC MOTOR

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we have reported the design, development and characterization of electrostatic motor. The electrostatic motors were fabricated using 3D printing technology and CAD software the Solid Works. Two type of motors were designed 1) the direct type electrostatic motor and 2) induction type electrostatic motor. The maximum speed of 1050RPM was achieved in direct type electrostatic motor at applied voltage of 5kV. In induction type motor the maximum speed of 1700RPM was achieved at 5kV. The induction type motor was only working with smaller size of rotor whereas the direct type of electrostatic motor was operated successfully in small and large size of rotors.

INTRODUCTION

Miniaturization of devices is one of the target areas of this era for reducing energy and materials demand, easy transport, and smart functionality [1-3]. An example is motors and other actuators which are now possible to fabricate in micro size [4,5]. The micro size motors are being fabricated using MEMS technology [6-9]. However, depending on motor types their processing steps may be so easy or very complex [10-13]. Electrostatic motor is the first ever invented motors in the history of motors that has an important contribution in micro actuation devices. They have

extensive application in the field of robotics, micro electromechanical systems (MEMS), and in the field of biomedical instruments, mainly because of its small size, simple operating mechanism, and good scalability. They work on the Coulombs electrostatic force generated between two electrodes that are oppositely charged. This mechanism permits for compact design, less complexity in the process of fabrication, and easy miniaturization, that makes electrostatic motors appropriate for its integration into large number of small scale and low power systems [14]. The parts of electrostatic motors are made of dielectric materials or

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metals that can easily accumulate and store charges on their surface. The resulted electrostatic force generated between the surface of rotor and stator results in the rotation of rotor. It is enabling the motion of these motors in micro and Nano scale devices [15].

In contact based electrostatic motors, the stator electrodes are in direct contact with poles of rotors. Due to this contact charges directly flows to the poles of rotors, after the accumulation of the charges on the rotor these charges generate repulsive force due to same nature of charges. On the other hand, the other the part of rotor that is repelled by one electrode is now attracted due by the opposite electrode due to opposite nature of charges [16].

The non-contact electrostatic motors work on principle of electrostatic changing capacitance and dielectric relaxation. These motors are further divided into two types 1) changing capacitance also known as electrostatic induction motors and 2) dielectric relaxation-based motors. The basic mechanism of both motors is based on capacitance between rotor and stator of motor, in which voltage is only supplied to stator electrodes. This voltage of the stator induces charges on the surface of rotor, which creates an electrostatic force between rotor and stator which results in the actuation of these motors. Anyhow, both types avoid direct contact between parts of motors, that results in efficient and smooth rotation of rotors and yields in better rotational output. These types of motors are prepared due its durability and avoiding of charge leakage [17].

Owing to their less power consumption, operating of static electricity, scalability, and their high precision, electrostatic motors are now a day broadly used in the field of MEMS, robotic, optical micro mirrors, and in the field biomedical micro scale devices [xx]. Its application in all these fields is critical due to mechanical stability and small requirement of small interfaces. On the other hand, their application is further expended due to their actuation by new nano generator technologies such as TENG, which is already suitable for charging of capacitors and better in accumulation of charges on dielectric surfaces [18-20]. Thus, their integration with such technologies has increased the role of electrostatic motors in self powered systems and micro robotics [21]. In this paper we are reporting the design and fabrication of number of electrostatic motors. These motors are designed in CAD software Solid Works and fabricated using additive manufacturing technology. The fabricated motors are operated on optimum voltages and voltages to speed relations are given.

MATERIALS

PLA filament was purchased from Alibaba, high voltage power supply from Griffin UK, aluminum tape purchased locally, Ender 3D printer from China.

METHOD:

Fabrication of electrostatic motor

The fabrication of an electrostatic motor designed using SolidWorks involves a carefully controlled and highly precise process, where each component is modeled to achieve an accuracy of up to ± 0.1 mm. The motor is designed in various shapes with diameters ranging from 0.9 cm to 6 cm and heights from 0.5 cm to 6 cm. For each motor two CAD files were developed 1) the rotor, 2) the stator. The rotor which serves as the movable electrode and is modeled in cylindrical form which is provided with stripes which are evenly spaced along its circumference. These stripes are installed on the rotor which was designed using the pattern in Solid Works, with each stripe dimensioned using the Smart Dimension tool to ensure high precision. The part which remains fixed is stator. After 3D printing of stator positive and negative electrodes were installed in it.

Rotors design: Two varieties of rotors were designed for direct and induction type electrostatic motors. The direct type rotor was designed with four segments where a conductor layer needs to deposit as shown in Figure 1. The induction type rotor is without any segment as shown in figure 2. Both of the rotors were designed in different size. The touching type rotors were designed in five sizes i) 0.9cm, 0.5cm in diameter and height respectively ii) 1.1cm, 0.8cm in diameter and height respectively, iii) 2cm, 1.5cm in diameter and height respectively iv) 4cm, 3cm in diameter and height respectively, and v) 6cm, 5cm in diameter and height respectively.

The induction type was designed in two sizes i) 0.9cm, 0.5cm in diameter and height respectively ii) 1.1cm, 0.8cm in diameter and height respectively. The larger size rotors were not working in induction type motors. All of these rotors were designed in light weight so that it can work with smaller amount of charge.

Figure 1: Top and tilt view of rotor with 4 segments

Figure 2: Tilt and top view of rotor without any segment

Stators design: Two types of stator were designed for direct type and induction type electrostatic motors. The CAD of both stators is shown in figure 3. The direct type rotor can work in both of the stators however the induction type can only work in a stator with open space where only electrodes need to arrange closely to rotor. The congested stator gets charge in few seconds which hinders the induction of rotor to rotate it.

Figure 3: CAD images of a) Direct type (touching type) stator, b) Induction type Stator

3D Printing: The CAD files were converted in STL format in Solids Work in which the slicing detail is saved for 3D printing. Further the STL files were converted in G-code in which the printing parameters are saved such as i) printing temperature (printing nozzle temperature) ii) bed temperature iii) printer type and dimensions iv) printing

speed, v) nozzle size, vi) support type, vii) adhesion type, viii) layer thickness, ix) printing density, x) printing height, xi) print position, and xii) printing material etc. All these parameters are set in Cura before making G-code. The G-code is then entered in 3D printer for printing the given model. The G-code guide the 3D printer according to all given and many other parameters which control each step of stepper motors in during 3D printing. All the files were printed with Ender 3 3D printer as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Camera image of Ender 3 pro 3D printer

Assembling: The 3D printed parts were assembled to form electrostatic motors. Before assembling the metallic shaft was installed in each rotor. Depending to its size the shafts were made from common pen and netting needles. The aluminum tape was pasted on each segment of touching type rotor. The stators were wired with either two or four wires.

Actuation of motors: These motors were actuated using Griffin high voltage power supply which gives output voltage from 100V to 5kV. These motors were also actuated with capacitors which were charged using TENG.

Speed measurement: The rotational speed (RPMs) of fabricated motors was measured using stroboscope. The stroboscope was also designed locally using Arduino uno, LED panel, LCD screen, rotary encoder and switch. The stroboscope flashes LED light which is focused on rotor and its pulse frequency is adjusted using rotary encoder which is displayed on LCD as RPM. During adjustment when the rotor appears stationary its RPM is read out from LCD.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fabricated electrostatic motors are mainly divided into i) Direct type and ii) induction type motors. Each type consists

of a rotor and a stator. The difference between two types is in direct type the electrodes touches rotor during running which need less voltage to operate because the charge is directly transferred to rotor. In induction type the air between electrode and rotor ionized and deposited charge on rotor. The induction type of electrostatic motor need higher voltage, which should be enough to ionize air between rotor and electrode. Such motors are high speed and highly efficient because there is very less friction.

i) Direct type electrostatic motor

Figure shows the CAD file, fabrication result and assembly of direct type electrostatic motor. The rotor has a very light structure which has four segments and a hole in the center for installing shaft. On each segment a aluminum sheet was pasted to make it conductive as shown in figure 5 (c). The stator is designed such as it can be used for different sizes of rotors and number of electrodes can be fit in it with different orientations. The stator has a central hole for installing rotor. The complete assembly of direct type electrostatic motor is shown in figure 5(e).

Figure 5: a) CAD image of direct type rotor, b,c) Top and tilt view of 3D printed rotor, d) CAD image of stator, e) Complete assembly of direct type electrostatic motor

The working mechanism of direct type of electrostatic motor is as follows: when a segment comes in front of positive electrode. The positive electrode extract few of electrons from the metallic surface of segment which causes to charge is positively. After getting charge the positive electrode repels positive surface of segment. Similarly, the opposite side segment gets negative charge and repels by negative electrode which make it move.

The output performance of electrostatic motor was tested with different structural parameters and different operating

voltages. In direct type total of five direct electrostatic motors were fabricated. These motors are named as DESM 1, DESM 2, DESM 3, DESM 4, and DESM 5.

DESM 1

Rotor diameter = 0.9cm

Rotor height = 0.5cm

Rotor effective area = $\pi dh = 3.14 \times 0.9 \times 0.5 = 1.4 \text{ cm}^2$

The motor was subjected to varying voltage and the respective speed in round per minutes (RPM) was recorded. The plot between voltage and speed is given in figure 6. This motor reaches to maximum speed of 1030RPM at 5kV. The minimum operating voltage was 550V where its speed was 760RPM.

Figure 6: Plot between voltage and speed of MESM 1 motor

MESM 2

Rotor diameter = 1.1cm

Rotor height = 0.8cm

Rotor effective area = $\pi dh = 3.14 \times 1.1 \times 0.8 = 2.76 \text{ cm}^2$

The motor was subjected to varying voltage and the respective speed in round per minutes (RPM) was recorded. The plot between voltage and speed is given in figure 7. This motor reaches to maximum speed of 900 RPM at 5kV. The minimum operating voltage was 450V where its speed was 660RPM.

Figure 7: Plot between voltage and speed of MESM 2 motor

MESM 3

Rotor diameter = 2 cm

Rotor height = 1.5cm

Rotor effective area = $\pi dh = 3.14 \times 2\text{cm} \times 1.5\text{cm} = 9.42 \text{ cm}^2$

The motor was subjected to varying voltage and the respective speed in round per minutes (RPM) was recorded. The plot between voltage and speed is given in figure 8. This motor reaches to maximum speed of 750 RPM at 5kV. The minimum operating voltage was 1kV where its speed was 400RPM.

Figure 8: Plot between voltage and speed of MESM 3 motor

MESM 4

Rotor diameter = 4 cm

Rotor height = 3cm

Rotor effective area = $\pi dh = 3.14 \times 4\text{cm} \times 3\text{cm} = 37.68\text{cm}^2$

The motor was subjected to varying voltage and the respective speed in round per minutes (RPM) was recorded. The plot between voltage and speed is given in figure 9. This motor reaches to maximum speed of 400 RPM at 5kV. The minimum operating voltage was 1.5kV where its speed was 300RPM.

Figure 9: Plot between voltage and speed of MESM 4 motor

MESM 5

Rotor diameter = 6cm

Rotor height = 5cm

Rotor effective area = $\pi dh = 3.14 \times 6 \times 5 = 94.2 \text{ cm}^2$

The motor was subjected to varying voltage and the respective speed in round per minutes (RPM) was recorded. The plot between voltage and speed is given in figure 10. This motor reaches to maximum speed of 360 RPM at 5kV. The minimum operating voltage was 1.5kV where its speed was 240RPM.

Figure 10: Plot between voltage and speed of MESM 5 motor

From above analysis it is clear that motor speed increases with increase in voltage. The speed decreases on increasing size at the same voltage. This is due to weight of rotor where higher weight rotor needs to be operated on high voltage.

ii) Induction type electrostatic motor

Figure 11 shows the CAD file; fabrication result and assembly of induction type electrostatic motor. The router has a very light structure which has cylindrical shape with a hole in the center for installing shaft. The stator is designed such as it can be used for different sizes of rotors and number of electrodes can be fit in it with different orientations. The stator has a central hole for installing rotor. The complete assembly of induction type electrostatic motor is shown in figure 11(c).

Figure 11: a) CAD image of rotor for induction type electrostatic motor, b) 3D print of given rotor, c) Complete assembly of induction type electrostatic motor.

The working mechanism of this motor is same as that of direct type with exception that electrodes do not touch rotor and the air ionizes in the gape to charge the router.

This type of motor only works in small size of rotor where the diameter is less than 1.2 cm. The induction motor was only operating at voltage more than 1kV and maximum speed of 1700 RPM was achieved at 5kV which the maximum limit of our power supply was.

CONCLUSION

Miniaturized electrostatic motors were successfully fabricated using 3D printing technology. Two types of electrostatic motors were fabricated with variety of sizes. The maximum speed of 1050RPM was achieved in direct type electrostatic motor at applied voltage of 5kV. In induction type motor the maximum speed of 1700RPM was achieved at 5kV. The induction type motor was only working with smaller size of rotor whereas the direct type of electrostatic motor was successfully operated from small to large size. In direct type motor that rotor speed increases with increase in voltage. The speed decreases on increasing size at the same voltage. This is due to weight of rotor where higher weight rotor needs to be operated on higher voltages.

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